

Evolution of the Copernicus DEM: beyond today's elevation data with WorldDEM Neo

Ernest Fahrland, Hanne Paschko, Henning Schrader

Airbus DS, SAR Programs

Potsdam, Germany

ernest.fahrland@airbus.com

hanne.paschko@airbus.com

henning.schrader@airbus.com

Virginia Herrera

Airbus DS, SAR Programs

Friedrichshafen, Germany

virginia.herrera@airbus.com

Abstract— The Copernicus DEM has established a programme-level reference for Digital Elevation Models, serving all Copernicus elements (Space, Services and In-situ) over a large array of Earth-Observation based applications. Originating from the TanDEM-X SAR-mission, interferometric data have been acquired between December 2010 and January 2015 to process a global, homogenous and highly accurate Digital Surface Model (DSM), which has been made available to ESA and its partners in a 10m resolution version. The 30m and 90m resolution versions have been made available to the general public. The value-adding of the TanDEM-X DEM (removal of terrain artefacts and hydrologic editing) conducted by Airbus created the WorldDEM™ dataset, which served as input for Copernicus DEM.

Based on the source data of the Copernicus DEM (WorldDEM) and fresh data acquisitions (2017-2020), a new generation of global DEM has been developed and validated which show improvements in actuality (2017-2020) and level of detail due to its new grid spacing of 5m. The global SAR-based DSM is commercially available as “WorldDEM Neo” with fully automated production processes, so as the DTM that is currently in production. Furthermore, known deficiencies in WorldDEM Neo caused by side-looking SAR (layover, shadow, high-rise buildings) are compensated through advanced processing. This comprises the local/regional integration of high-resolution DEM data from evolving techniques such as SAR image reconstruction or from optical sensors (primarily for DSM).

This document will focus on the processes to create an up-to-date high-resolution DSM/DTM on a global scale and the prospect of serving further applications in the Copernicus / Sentinel ecosystem.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital elevation information (DSM, DTM) are an essential information source for various scientific and commercial applications. The Copernicus DEM & WorldDEM (acquired

2010-2015), ALOS World 3D (2006-2011) and SRTM (2000) are well-established DSMs though the data is not up-to-date. As Earth's surface is very dynamic, current height information is as important as a high degree of precision. A huge challenge for global elevation information is the transformation of raw/unedited elevation information into edited, analysis-ready elevation information.

In section II, a fully automated production process for global DSM data starting with unedited TanDEM-X Change DEM (German Space Agency; DLR) is described. This comprises the automated compensation of artefacts as well as hydro editing to produce the global WorldDEM Neo dataset. Section III provides the results of a statistical analysis based on ICESat-2 ATL08 point data and a visual example of WorldDEM Neo. An outlook on the subsequent integration of alternate DEM data to improve WorldDEM Neo and further processing to derive global DTM data is provided in section IV.

II. METHODS

A. Input Datasets

1) WorldDEM as input for Copernicus DEM

The current version of the Copernicus DEM is primarily derived from the commercial WorldDEM offered by Airbus DS with substitutions of the nominal fill sources by national DEM data for the area of Norway and Spain. WorldDEM is based on the unedited version of the TanDEM-X DEM (DLR). The generation process and performance of the TanDEM-X DEM is described in [1]. A description of the editing process to create the WorldDEM is available in [2]. The technical specification of the WorldDEM dataset is provided hereafter.

TABLE I. WORLDDEM PARAMETERS

Acquisition timeframe		Dec. 2010 – Jan. 2015
Coverage		Global / pole-to-pole
Projection		Geographic coordinates
Data Tiling		1° x 1°
Coordinate reference system	horizontal	WGS84-G1150
	vertical	EGM2008
Pixel spacing	latitude (Y)	0,4" (~12m)
	longitude (X)	0,4" – 4,0" (~12m, dep. on latitude)

2) TanDEM-X Change rawDEM scenes

DLR and Airbus DS decided in 2016 to acquire an additional global coverage of bi-static DEM data, after finishing the TanDEM-X DEM. The looking direction of the so-called Change DEM acquisitions is opposite to the one from the nominal TanDEM-X data (acquired 2010-2015). The across-track overlap of the new DEM scenes is ~4-5 km (Figure 2) and the interferometric processing is based on the delta-phase algorithm described in [3]. Although the interferometric process is supported by WorldDEM (~30m), the new phase (height) values are independent. The ground sampling distance of the Change rawDEM scenes is 0,2" (~5-6m). To preserve the level of detail of the Change rawDEM scenes best, no additional process step is performed by DLR (mosaicking and calibration, MCP) as this would create a DEM with again 0,4" ground sampling distance (~12m). The Change raw DEM data is unedited.

Figure 1. TanDEM-X Change DEM coverage and DEM scene overlap

B. WorldDEM Neo production process

1) Process overview

The production process creates an analysis-ready DSM dataset in a short timeframe. User interaction to mitigate artefacts in the unedited Change rawDEM data is not applied and a fully automated production process in a high performance computing environment has been established. The following Figure 2 provides a graphical overview of the process structure.

Figure 2. Global coverage of WorldDEM / Copernicus DEM

2) Mosaicking of TanDEM-X Change rawDEM scenes

After data transfer from DLR and database import at Airbus, the Change rawDEM scenes are mosaicked. Overlap regions of the scenes (see zoom caption in Figure 2) are processed with priority on the more up-to-date scene. A feathering algorithm at the scene borders for a distance of 10 pixels ensures a consistent and homogenous representation of the final WorldDEM Neo. Auxiliary information required for subsequent processes and/or the final product comprise an incidence angle mask (IAM), height error mask (HEM), radar amplitude mosaic (AMP) and source scene mask (SCM).

3) DEM Fusion: Change rawDEM mosaic and WorldDEM

As the Change rawDEM mosaic represents unedited height information, a compensation of local artefacts based on DEM fusion has been developed. Reliable and fresh height information from the Change DEM acquisitions is preserved as much as possible, whereas unreliable height information is either compensated via alternate height information (weighted DEM fusion with WorldDEM) or edited acc. to pre-defined rules (hydro editing). A quality-based fusion principle based on the DEM height error is described in [4] and served as basis for process development. The height error is available in form of the standard deviation on a pixel basis and derived from the radar coherence and geometrical considerations. The weight of the Change rawDEM mosaic is derived with the following procedure.

$$w_{CD} = \frac{\frac{1}{\sigma_{HEMCD} \sqrt[4]{|\Delta Z|}}}{\frac{1}{\sigma_{HEMCD} \sqrt[4]{|\Delta Z|}} + \frac{1}{(s \times \sigma_{HEMWd}) \sqrt[4]{|\Delta Z|}}}$$

The pixel-based height errors for the Change rawDEM and WorldDEM are represented by σ_{HEMCD} resp. σ_{HEMWd} . The absolute height difference between both DEMs is represented by $|\Delta Z|$. The stretch factor s for σ_{HEMWd} is based on geometrical considerations (local slope gradient, incidence angle (IAM) incl. variable margin), the absolute height difference $|\Delta Z|$ and three additional parameters. The following Figure 3 displays the stretch factor scenario for a sample incidence angle of 40°.

Figure 3. Stretch factor for σ_{HEMWD} with a radar incidence angle of 40°

For steep terrain in combination with a steep incidence angle, the stretch factor reduces the height error of WorldDEM, i.e. this height information is superior to the one from Change DEM. For moderate to plain terrain in combination with a low absolute height difference, the stretch factor is almost 1 and the weighting between the two DEMs is balanced. With an increasing absolute height difference, the height error of WorldDEM is raised, i.e. the Change DEM gains increasing superiority compared to WorldDEM. The final weighting is integrated in the final WorldDEM Neo product (in percent, weighted combination mask, WCM).

4) Editing of fused DEM

Hydrological features are subject to changes in extent as well as water level throughout time. For instance, ocean shoreline can change due to coastal erosion or harbor construction. Lakes and reservoirs can have different water extent/level. River courses can have changed. An automated process for delineation and vertical levelling process has been developed with the support of the hydrological information created during the WorldDEM editing process [2]. The editing information is integrated in the final WorldDEM Neo product (editing mask, EDM).

5) Statistical analysis based on ICESat-2 ATL08

A global statistical analysis using ICESat-2 laser altimetry data (ATL08, [5]) was applied on WorldDEM Neo. A filtering of the (reference) point data is based on the following attributes:

- Sole `h_te_best_fit_20m` elevation without parallel presence of canopy height information
- `h_te_uncertainty` < 7,5m
- No hydro editing during production process

Regions with permanent snow/ice cover (Antarctica, Greenland) have been excluded. The generalized slope gradient of

WorldDEM Neo ($\sim 30m$) is used to categorize the ICESat-2 ATL08 point data. The point count for slopes of 0° - 10° is significantly higher compared to slopes $>10^\circ$.

TABLE II. STATISTICAL RESULTS FOR WORLDDEM NEO BASED ON ICESAT-2 ATL08 TERRAIN POINTS (`h_te_best_fit_20M`)

Slope	LE90	RMSE	ATL08 point count	
0° - 10°	1,350 m	0,961 m	2'553'468'984	99,404 %
10° - 20°	4,979 m	3,122 m	14'201'213	0,553 %
20° - 30°	11,110 m	7,315 m	961'622	0,037 %
30° - 40°	16,882 m	12,695 m	125'519	0,005 %
40° +	29,211 m	22,636 m	15'511	0,001 %
TOTAL	1,375 m	0,976 m	2'568'772'849	100 %

III. RESULTS

A. Visual example

The following Figure 4 provides a visual comparison of WorldDEM and WorldDEM Neo for an area North of the city of Lanzhou in China ($36,45^\circ N$, $103,75^\circ E$; incl. radar image overlay).

Figure 4. Comparison display of WorldDEM (top) and WorldDEM Neo (bottom) for an area North of Lanzhou (China)

B. WorldDEM Neo Technical Specification

WorldDEM Neo is compliant to independent DEM standards (DGED Level 4b, INSPIRE Level 17) and is specified according to the table below.

TABLE III. WORLDDDEM NEO PARAMETERS

Acquisition timeframe		2017 - 2020
Coverage		Global / pole-to-pole
Projection		Geographic coordinates
Data Tiling		0,5° x 0,5°
Coordinate reference system	horizontal	WGS84-G1150
	vertical	EGM2008
Pixel spacing	latitude (Y)	0,15" (~5m)
	longitude (X)	0,15" – 1,5" (~5m, dep. on latitude)

IV. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

WorldDEM Neo represents the most up-to-date global Digital Surface Model with a high level of detail and accuracy. The production is based on a fully automated and parameterizable python process, which allows easy adaptation and fast WorldDEM Neo re-processing to encompass future user requirements (e.g. new timestamp based on additional future acquisitions).

A. Global DTM with new temporal footprint

A wide range of DEM applications (e.g. hydrology, risk management, geology) require bare ground elevation information with vegetation, buildings, etc. removed. WorldDEM Neo opens the possibility for an improved global Digital Terrain Model (DTM) due to the higher level of detail and the fresh data acquisition compared to current DTMs originating from TanDEM-X (WorldDEM DTM LITE, FABDEM [6]). WorldDEM Neo DTM will close the gap of providing a global coverage while offering more detailed terrain structure and time update.

The WorldDEM Neo DTM production process (knowledge-based set of rules) is based on the identification and description of surface objects within the DSM followed by a transformation of the surface heights into terrain heights while conserving the characteristics of the underlying terrain. The fully automated and parameterizable process is closed by an automated quality control and a visual check (if required).

Figure 5. Example of WorldDEM Neo DSM and WorldDEM Neo DTM for an area West of Munich (Germany; 48,25°N, 11,25°E))

B. Local/regional quality improvement of WorldDEM Neo

Side looking radar technology can cause deficiencies in a DSM that can be isolated to specific regions of the Earth, e.g. urban areas and regions with very steep slopes.

Analyses show that interferometric DSM data can benefit from height information derived from stereo-optical imagery or evolving techniques such as DEM reconstruction (based on single SAR imagery). The experiences with the Delta Surface Fill Method (DSF, [7]) from the WorldDEM production support the combination of the various Digital Surface Models from different sources. A “zero mean plane” within the DSF process ensures least adaptations to the alternate height information, i.e. without introducing systematic shifts and seamlines.

C. Regional updates of WorldDEM Neo beyond 2020

The on-going bistatic orbit configuration of TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X and the available satellite resources allow additional DEM acquisitions, which can be used to further update the current version of WorldDEM Neo.

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